

PREVALENCE OF CYTOMEGALOVIRUSES IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE.

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Actuality of the problem. Currently, cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection causes premature abortions and infertility in women all over the world. Most of the CMV risk group are children aged 5-6 years and adults aged 15-30 years, as well as women of childbearing age. Particularly dangerous is the infection with this virus in the 1-3 month of pregnancy, which in many cases ends in miscarriage [1-6]. During pregnancy, 35-50% of women become infected with the virus, and in 8-10% of cases, the life of the mother and child is at risk as a result of reactivation of the infection [7-12].

Objective of the study. Study of the prevalence of cytomegaloviruses in women of reproductive age.

Material and methods of the study. In this study, 120 women of reproductive age were identified, and 40 women of the same age with negative results for antibodies to cytomegalovirus in blood serum, determined by ELISA and rapid testing, were selected as a control group [13,14,15].

Results and discussion. The first group of women of reproductive age selected for the study consisted of 20 girls aged 16-18, the second group of 40 girls aged 19-22, the third group of 30 girls aged 23-25, the fourth group of 15 women aged 26-30, and the 5th group of women over 31 years old. IgM and IgG antibodies in the blood serum were preliminarily determined by the express test method and confirmed by the ELISA method. According to the results of the examination, 5% IgM, 25% IgG were detected in the first group, 10% IgM, 65% IgG in the second group, 6.7% IgM, 46.7% IgG in the third group, 6.7% IgM, 33.3% IgG in the fourth group, 0% IgM, 33.3% IgG in the 5th group. According to the results of the general indicators in the control group, it was found that the women had 6.7% IgM and 45.83% IgG in their blood serum. As a result of these results, it was found that complications in the fetus and childbirth differed significantly from those in the control group.

Conclusions. The results showed that 6.7% of women of reproductive age have IgM antibodies to CMV and 45.83% have IgG antibodies to CMV. When

analyzing the results of the examination and studying the negative impact of the CMV virus on the fetus and pregnancy, it was found that the first group is 15%, the second group - 17.5%, the third group - 20%, the fourth group 13.3%, and the fifth group - 20%, and for the general group this figure was 17.5%.

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